

Postcolonial Vision In V.S Naipaul's Half A Life And Magic Seeds

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Abstract

V.S. Naipaul is a pivotal figure in contemporary postcolonial literature. As a man shaped and defined by two cultures, East and West, he expresses in his works the psychology of people living in the third world and the obstacles he encountered as a rootless person in his search for a cultural and spiritual home. Naipaul's stories are, in fact, the histories of former imperialist colonies prior to their withdrawal. He wrote about the sentiment of a person who is not in his native land but in a colony, but whose sadness emanates from his heart and induces a melancholic state of mind. This paper aims to bring out the postcolonial vision of Naipaul in *Half a Life* and *Magic Seeds*. The theme of placelessness, unbelongingness and identity crisis is presented powerfully in these works.

Key words: post-colonial, third world, identity crisis, unbelongingness.

Introduction

V.S. Naipaul is one of the greatest writers of our generation, having published more best-sellers than many of his contemporaries. Though he is primarily a Caribbean writer of Indian descent, he has carved out a place for himself in English-language world literature. In 1971, he was awarded the Booker Prize, and in 2001, he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature. He was born in the year 1932. The works of V.S. Naipaul were released at regular intervals from 1957 to 2004, comprising approximately thirty volumes and numerous reprints. Naipaul is well-known on the international scene, having amassed an impressive collection of books and awards to his credit. All of his artwork is influenced by themes such as alienation, displacement, rootlessness, mockery, and self-deception. Fictional works such as novels, short stories, and essays constitute the vast majority of Naipaul's writings.

V.S. Naipaul established himself as a major figure in the history of postcolonial Indian Diasporic literature. He is the unifying figure in the history of English literature. Naipaul is a meticulous artist who understands the value of the past in the artistic enterprise. His sole focus is on the various facets of identity. He initially constructs the web of identity through a variety of characters in a variety of situations and time periods, including colonial and post-colonial periods. His depictions of Indians are indispensable. He is considered a forerunner

of Indian identity. He, successfully, combines myth and reality, multiculturalism, Hinduism, modernism, and traditionalism. As a novelist of the colonial experience, he situates his works in colonial and post-colonial societies, vividly capturing the complexities inherent in such societies.

Postcolonial Methodology

V. S. Naipaul is a postcolonial writer. Why he should be considered as a post-colonial writer some definitions of postcolonial criticism are given to prove. John McLeod, in *Beginning Post -Colonialism*, states that postcolonial criticism involves one or more of such activities as:

[...] Reading texts produced by writers from countries with a history of colonialism.[...] reading texts produced by those that have migrated from countries with a history of colonialism, or those descended from migrant families, which deal in the main with diaspora experience and its many consequences.(McLeod)

This definition shows that Naipaul is covered by the range of postcolonial literary analysis. Similarly, Robert Young in *Post-Colonialism: A Historical Introduction* points out that:

Postcolonial theory has always been concerned with the positive and negative consequences of peoples and cultures colliding, whether through colonial domination and the transmutation of indigenous cultures or through the hybridization of domestic metropolitan cultures as a result of immigration. (Young)

The positive and negative effects of the mixing of peoples and cultures as a result of colonial domination is an obvious theme that can be found in all his works. As a keen observer of civilizations, cultures, and histories across the world, Naipaul has gradually occupied a coveted place along with some of the most celebrated modern writers like Neil Bissondath, Bharati Mukherjee, Samuel Selvon, Seepersad Naipaul, etc. in exploring and interrogating the colonial and post-colonial issues and realities that have shaped the contemporary societies and their politics. No doubt, he has perceived every facet of man's relationship with power, authority, and oppression. His absorption of the experience of rootlessness, the alienating effects of the colonial past on the prevalent postcolonial people has taken him to Africa, South America, and India.

Postcolonial Vision In Half A Life And Magic Seeds

V.S. Naipaul has written about the impact of postcolonialism and orientalist thought on people living in third-world countries, among other things, Willie Chandran, the protagonist of *Half a Life* (2001), is confronted with the implications of migration in a postcolonial setting. The author claims that being Portuguese in Africa, a Caribbean man in London, an Indian woman married to a German man, a Brahmin married to a "backward" - all of these confusing conditions result in "half a life".

Throughout his books, colonists arrive and conquer, empires rise and fall, and new cultures emerge, yet sadness pervades colonial and postcolonial life, accompanied by illusory hopes of assimilation, which are never realized. He has written candidly about his own life experiences, which has earned him acclaim. Rob Nixon writes:

Naipaul's familial and personal displacements figure so boldly in both his work and its critical reception that he has come to be celebrated as the ultimate literary partied, the most comprehensively uprooted of twentieth-century writers, and the most devoid of national affiliations. (Nixon)

He uses his displacements and the weight of unresolved differences as a framework for his works, which in some ways helps to explain his writings. Naipaul feels remote and estranged from everyone and

everything he encounters. He has made derogatory remarks about Trinidad and Tobago, India, the United States, Pakistan, and Argentina, among other places, says Nanda Kishore Mishra in his article "*Trajectory of Displacement: Expatriate Sensibility of Naipaul*". When he returns to India after his tour, he discovers that his dreams have been completely dashed, and his hatred for India becomes apparent.

In Naipaul's *Half a Life*, the main character, Willie Somerset Chandran, is an Indian by birth, having been raised by a Brahmin father and a Dalit mother. Willie Chandran has emerged as a voice for the innumerable migrants who are sacrificing their lives daily in the Syrian refugee crisis. Despite the fact that Willie and his father's unrelenting yearning for modernity ultimately led to Willie's journey, they have left behind a legacy of exile and unease as a foreigner. The colonial people's futile attempts to fit themselves into their surroundings are demonstrated by the borrowed part of Willie's name "Somerset". It is the story of Willie's search for his identification and his relocation in *Half a Life*. This novel, like many of Naipaul's other writings, incorporates elements that are based on his own life. Seeking to carve himself a distinct identity and a place in the world that he can call his own, Willie is attempting to develop a sense of belonging. He has earned the title of an exiled Indian as a result of his uprooting and displacement.

The novel *Half a Life* is divided into three major parts. The first chapter is titled A Visit from Somerset, and it is set in the county of Somerset. In this chapter, Maugham describes Willie's boyhood and early youth through the eyes of Willie's father, who serves as the chapter's narrator as well as the protagonist. A scholarship enables Willie's father, a product of Naipaul's half-made society, to direct the course of his son's life. Willie is sent to London to pursue higher study with the assistance of a scholarship. The title of the second chapter refers to Willie's experiences at London College and in Notting Hill, which is described in the third-person narrative style. It is significant because it marks the beginning of the first chapter of Willie's life, which begins with the start of this chapter. The third chapter, A Second Translation, is

titled as such because it deals with Willie's second and final translation in his life. This chapter tells the story of Willie's trip through Africa and to an undiscovered island. During his journey to Africa, Willie comes face to face with the true emptiness of his existence. William is approximately forty-one years old when the novel *Half a Life* concludes. Towards the end of the work, the narrative shifts from third-person to the first-person narrative, which is a significant change. *Half a Life's* sequel *Magic Seeds* (2004), follows up where *Half a Life* leaves off in Berlin, where the first half of the film ends. The story had begun in Berlin a long time ago. "We're on a different planet".

In *Magic Seeds*, Willie's five months in Berlin, seven to eight years in India, and his life in London are combined to form a narrative that proclaims the entire concept of Willie's life "... in a setting he had perhaps not yet learned to recognize, he was like a man who had been ripped from within himself. A new persona had been created for him" (3). This novel comes to a close when Willie is fifty-two years old, thanks to the use of third-person narrative to bring the story to a close. For his part, Naipaul is a great believer in the concept of creating one's own identity rather than being given one. The name of a person has a significant role in constructing his or her identity. Willie Somerset Chandran's middle name is Willie Somerset Chandran. As Homi Bhaba's idea of "mimicry" (90), Somerset alludes to colonial people's attempts to replicate colonizers, such as Indians imitating the behavior of Britishers, as an example of colonial people. "In mimicry, the representation of identity and meaning is rearticulated along the axis of metonymy", writes Homi K. Bhaba in his book *The Location of Culture*. "In mimicry, the representation of identity and meaning is rearticulated along the axis of metonymy". The process of re-articulation of identity representation is nothing more than a copying of the ideology that is now in place. The ability to mimic the other object while also emulating the dominant ideology can be achieved, but this is generally at the expense of one's individuality. What happens as a result of slavishly replicating Western concepts is exactly what we are seeing right now. Consequently, this naming technique results in a chain of misnaming events to

follow. One of the themes explored in this work is the detrimental consequences of colonialism, particularly on the psyche of indigenous peoples. People who were formerly oppressed are now forced to live half-lives in a postcolonial world where they are no longer considered equal. "Willie is the most eloquent illustration of this half-heartedness of existence" (268). Almost all of Naipaul's characters are on a quest to discover the meaning and purpose of their lives. According to Ashwini Kumar Vishnu's critique of *Half a Life*:

A Reading in Sense, Sensibility, and Sensuality, Percy Cato, Marcus, Graca, Ana, Sarojini, Jacinto, Ricardo, Carla, Noronhas, Correias, Aivaró, and the rest of the characters are all yearning for the completion of their lives. Percy Cato, Marcus, Graca "When it comes to their quest for fulfillment and self-realization, they find themselves clinging to unforeseen circumstances. They have no choice but to thrive in what so ever circumstances they find themselves in. (Kumar)

The characters in *Half A Life* have no choice but to cling to the false promise of assimilation in the end, and this is true for every character in *Half A Life*. And the lives of the people of the Orient are determined by their desire for identity as well as by inequality. They are always seeking to fit themselves into western cultural frameworks and ideologies. Neither do they remain orientated nor do they become occident during this phase, though. In both cases, human effort is at the heart of the matter; they are partly affirmation and partly identification with the other. In postcolonial discourses, the question of where culture is located is raised. In every place in the globe, some climbers are "forgetting about who they are", and, on the other hand, there are climbers who "remember where they came from" (Fanon). Willie is unable to find solace anywhere, even in his home state of Michigan. Afterward, his attempts to mix in with other cultures proved to be fruitless. Seraph's borrowed girlfriends are Serafina, June, and Gracie, the wife of the new boss. However, their relationships are short-lived, as is his. His associations with Graca add more complications to his life. Ana is the one who finds out about it. It contributes to the whole set of his homelessness. While going

through this process, he loses all sense of who he is, according to Fanon. Willie makes his declaration:

The moment Ana walked through the door of the hospital, I mustered the courage to tell her I wanted to divorce her. When she returned later, I informed her that I was forty-one years old. I'm fed up with being a part of your universe. Willie, you were the one who desired it. You enquired, and we responded. I'll have to think about it. (Naipaul *Half a Life*)

Despite the fact that Willie contacts Ana about the divorce, Ana recognizes that she won't be able to make a decision immediately. But one thing is certain: neither of them is satisfied with the other's performance. Everybody, including Willie, Percy Cato, Ana, Willie's father, and mother and Graca, as well as Willie's father and mother, is living a half-life. It is even those who appear to be living their own lives, such as Ana, who acknowledge that "it wasn't my life either". With the concept of the Postcolonial Migrant Thinker, Willie comes across as someone who embodies a universal state of hybridity. Think about Homi K. Bhabha's point of view on the migrant experience in the postcolonial world in this context. It is the evaluation of colonial identity that is founded on the repetition of discriminatory identity effects that is known as hybridity. In it, it is demonstrated how all institutions of bias and dominance must be deformed and dismantled. Displacing someone is evidence of discrimination in and of itself. Willie's uprooting and replication of English culture are very similar to his displacement and mimicry of English culture in the novel (Bhabha). It's no coincidence that the title of the novel *Half an Existence* perfectly captures the essence of someone's life as they migrate from one location to another in search of a unique identity and a sense of purpose. However, as a result of his alienation, he becomes baffled. The tragedy of Willie's life brings him closer to the meaning of life, just as Shakespeare's tragic drama brings him closer to the meaning of life. Willie's complaint about life's transience and harshness is comparable to Macbeth's complaint about life, except that Willie is not living his own life but is borrowing someone else's, and both are complaining about life. Additionally, Ana bears some similarities to

Willie's look. She, too, lives a half-life or aspires to borrow a life when she is in Willie's company, never really experiencing either. Ana, a mixed-caste person, and Graca are all characters who have numerous lives or are caught between two identities, including Willie's father, mother, and later Willie in India, London, and Africa, as well as Willie himself. It is supported by the half-lives of all of the story's protagonists that the title of the work is given its meaning. The time comes for Willie to leave Ana and Africa. Ashe explains to Ana, he has spent all of his mature years attempting to gain control of a life he could call his own, despite the fact that the life that was entrusted to him had become unimaginably unbelievable. Willie's life is divided into two halves: the half-completed journey of his life, and the half-fulfilled goals of his life, such as his desire to be a writer, which is also half-fulfilled. Willie's half-life comes to an end almost in the middle of the book, in the middle of his life at the age of forty-one, almost in the middle of the book (Colon). Consequently, the novel's title becomes wonderfully resonant when it comes to presenting lives caught between dualism and emptiness.

Half a Life and *Magic Seeds* are replete with literary allusions and allusions to Naipaul's own writings. The issues are identity crisis, belongingness and placelessness, and these characteristics are prevalent in the two novels *Half a Life* and *Magic Seeds*. The theme of placelessness, unbelongingness, and identity crisis is presented powerfully. These are the two primary characteristics that aid the author in developing his stories. Both novels are also conscious of a strong desire for independence and an identity crisis. His novels convey a sense of biography as his transitions from Trinidad to the cosmopolitan and multi-cultural culture of England. He is adamant that colonizers create colonial culture societies, and that those societies' knowledge and culture come from the outside.

Conclusion

Naipaul's view and people's reaction are summed up in his novels *Half a Life* and *Magic Seeds*. These two novels demonstrate how people's search for a home and a sense of belonging is hindered by two factors: first, the reality of homelessness, and second, the socio-cultural complexity unique to each

location. To put it another way, the reality of homelessness makes the yearning for a place to call home elusive. As a result, Willie, as a person with a hybrid identity, must pick between India (where he has familial ties), Africa (where his wife lives), and England as his habitat (rather than his home) (where he studies and pursue a career). Living in a multi-cultural materialist England might not be perfect for Willie, but it would be preferable to living under unstable, fragmented, and corrupt social structures. When asked what he liked about English society before the publication of the two novels, Naipaul said, "I think it's that people have worked out a nice method –perhaps the best way –of men getting along with men. I believe there is a tremendous sense of human need and right here”.

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